

Preferred Time Management Techniques Among Working Students

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Abstract:

Time management techniques are a set of principles that working students need to follow to optimize productivity and prioritize focus and organization. However, due to work pressure, working students are unable to focus on their studies. Working students find it hard to balance work and school. The research aimed to identify the preferred techniques for how working students manage their time. This study describes the overall intention of correlational research design. It was conducted in a Local City College and utilized a survey questionnaire to gather data. A random sampling method was used in this study to select working students in the School of Education, particularly Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED), Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Filipino (BSED Filipino), Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics (BSED Math), and Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English (BSED English) from 1st year to 3rd year. A self-made questionnaire was distributed among the respondents. Microsoft Excel was used to find the correlation between preferred time management techniques and the academic performance of the working students. Findings revealed that among the three preferred time management techniques: Short-term planning, long-term planning, and Time Attitude, it was revealed that Time Attitude is the most preferred technique of the working students interpreted as Often. This implies that the working students are enhancing efficiency in time management skills towards their study and work. Concerning the significant relationship between preferred time management techniques and academic performance, using the table of the level of significance of a one-tailed test, the null hypothesis was rejected. The study revealed that there is a significant relationship between preferred time management techniques and the academic performance of working students. Therefore, it is recommended that academic institutions provide workshops or training programs to enhance time management skills for working students to improve their academic performance.

Keywords: Time Management Techniques, Short-term Planning, Long-term Planning, Time Attitudes

Introduction:

Time management is important for working students to balance academic and work responsibilities. Time management is the process of using time effectively to accomplish tasks and goals. It is important to identify and prioritize tasks, schedule them appropriately, and allocate the necessary time and resources to perform them effectively. Effective time management leads to better academic performance and lower student anxiety levels. Individuals may increase productivity, minimize stress, and establish a better work-life balance by practicing good time management. However, students who cannot manage their time effectively can be hampered by the flexibility and freedom of the university atmosphere (SNAM Razali et al., 2018). Time management is definitely a challenge for working students, especially college students. It has been observed that time management is indeed difficult for working students as they must strike a balance between their obligations to their jobs, their academic work, and their personal lives. If not handled properly, this may result in stress and burnout. Finding time for both work and school frequently entails setting priorities and removing less crucial activities. Ahmed (2019) found that lack of proper time management skills in students is one of the main causes of high dropouts and poor academic performance. Students are expected to develop a functional lesson plan that covers all areas of the course and set aside time to read and study the course in order of importance. With this being said, the researchers have provided time management techniques that can aid working students who are currently employed for them to better use their time. This time management technique that the researchers came up with is expected to assist students in juggling their time between school and work.

Literature Review:

When students are balancing work and school, time management can be difficult. The management of one's professional and academic lives is no easy endeavor, whether one is working to pay for college or returning to school to advance their existing employment. This is especially true when one has extra obligations competing for their time, such as having children. Lack of time is not the issue; rather, it's how people use their time that counts. When it comes to time management advice, the advice to create a timetable is frequently near the top of the list for a good reason—it works (Logsdon, 2020). Making a timetable can assist generate order, which is the first step in efficiently managing their time. Start by listing all the fixed events that are not adjustable, such as class times and work, on a sheet of paper divided into thirty-minute segments. They will have a clearer idea of what they have to deal with when scheduling time to study and take care of their other obligations as a result of this. Again, this straightforward piece of advice might be

disregarded due to how uncomplicated it is, but it is one of the best things they can do, providing they adhere as closely as possible to the timetable they create. They put in a lot of effort and deserve some downtime to decompress and unwind, whether it entails taking a long bath or just drifting off to watch a few of their favorite TV series. They should always give themselves that time since it is crucial to success because they want to prevent burnout. As a result, individuals must acknowledge that they may occasionally need to skip or shorten this time spent doing nothing. It is beneficial to schedule a specific period of time for working and to alter the tasks you complete within that time. Reading the material in little doses helps them stay mentally engaged and may make them feel less worried than they might otherwise when thinking about finishing the complete assignment at once. They will feel pleased about the progress they have achieved on the numerous school-related chores since their minds are a little bit more clear (Ann Logsdon, 2020). Making better use of their time while attempting to balance their employment and education will be made possible by these helpful recommendations, which include scheduling your time, learning to make sacrifices, and working on eliminating procrastination. When a student thinks about these concepts, their stress levels decrease and they become more productive at work and in school. There are advantages and disadvantages to working while learning. With a job, kids can generate money. Some of these students need the money to pay for expensive colleges, while others need it to improve their quality of life. In addition to gaining work experience, they can grow more independent, build course-relevant abilities, learn how to budget and manage their time, and improve soft skills like communication and problem-solving. Being a working student is challenging and entails a lot of duties, according to Abenoja (2019). As a result, they experience a greater sense of control over their choices and actions. Students gain a lot of experiences and insights while working, which may help them in both their personal lives and problem-solving skills. As mentioned by (Mersa R. et al. 2022) in their study, students who choose to work, and study are facing difficulties both in work and school. They are often late for work and school and find it difficult to complete their assignments because they are exhausted from work. Tumin et al. (2020) stated in their study working students having difficulties in balancing work and study. Handling their obligations as a worker and student causes them difficulties, and could impact how they approach their academic work in the future. Student employment allegedly affects retention rates, according to (Lessky F. and Unger M. 2022). Students who work while in school may benefit in ways that increase their employability, for example, but too much work may have the opposite impact. As reported in their research, Acaso (2019) revealed that students are taking up part-time work to earn extra income. It significantly affects how well students succeed academically. This circumstance may have both been. The demands of balancing work and school can lead to increased stress and burnout for working students, as stipulated by Crawford et.al (2010). They argue that providing adequate resources and support can help these students better manage their time and reduce their stress levels. According to Masten, W. G et.al (2019), in their study, they found that planning is a crucial strategy for working students to manage their time effectively. Through their research, they identified several ways in which planning can benefit. Working with students includes helping them prioritize tasks and activities, reducing stress and anxiety related to time management, improving academic performance, and enhancing overall well-being and work-life balance. Eun (2018), in his study, found that planning is one of the most effective time management strategies for college students, including working students. Specifically, planning helps students prioritize tasks, set goals, and allocate time effectively. Planning also helps students stay on track and avoid procrastination. Additionally, Eun suggests that using a planner or digital calendar can be particularly helpful for working students who have busy schedules and multiple responsibilities. In an article entitled "Time Management Strategies for Working Students," Gupta, A. (2020), Gupta reviews various time management strategies that working students can use, including planning. Gupta notes that planning can help working students manage their time by allowing them to prioritize their tasks, set realistic goals, and create a schedule that accommodates both work and school obligations. By doing so, working students can avoid feeling overwhelmed, reduce stress, and achieve better academic and work performance. Working students are experts in time management, balancing work, and academics. They often have to juggle long hours at work, attend classes, complete assignments and projects on time, and still find time for themselves and their families. The skills they learn while managing their time and priorities can make them highly effective in their future careers, (Smith, J., 2019).

Research Method:

The study employed a Descriptive Correlational research design, focusing on investigating social issues using numerical data collection and statistical analysis methods like econometric models. The data were collected based on instruments created by the researcher from various sources. Correlational research was utilized to assess consistent fluctuations between variables, aiming to find relationships between them. The research was conducted at Mandaue City College, chosen because of the researchers' enrollment and the presence of working students in various programs like Education, Business, and Technology, overseen by designated Deans. The respondents were working students from the School of Education, particularly in Bachelor of Elementary Education, Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Filipino, Mathematics, and English from first to third years due to time and financial constraints. Inclusion criteria included students working since the 1st semester of the Academic Year 2022-2023 for at least six months, while exclusion criteria applied to fourth-year students due to practicum commitments. The researcher personally explained the study's purpose to the respondents and distributed a survey questionnaire focusing on academic performance and time management. Data collection involved a pre-survey, questionnaire distribution, validation by an expert, and statistical analysis using tools like weighted mean and Pearson's correlation coefficient. Ethical considerations ensured participant protection, voluntary consent, confidentiality, and respect throughout the research process. The study aimed to contribute insights into time management and academic achievement among working students, benefiting both participants and future researchers.

Results and Discussion:

Academic performance is a measure of a student's achievement in various educational activities, including exams, assignments, projects, and overall understanding of the subject matter. Strong academic performance is often associated with factors such as effective study habits, time management skills, engagement in learning activities, and a positive attitude towards education.

Table 1.
Academic Performance

The table presented the first semester General Weighted Average (GWA) of the students as a measure of the academic performance of the respondents.

General Weighted Average	Academic Performance	f	%
1.00	Excellent	0	0
1.1-1.5	Superior	11	19.30
1.6-2.0	Very Good	44	77.19
2.1-2.5	Good	2	3.51
2.6-3.0	Fair	0	0
Total		57	100%
GWA		1.76	Very Good

Legend: f-Frequency, %-Percentage, 1.00- Excellent, 1.1-1.5- Superior, 1.6-2.0-Very Good, 2.1-2.5-Good, 2.6-3.0-Fair

As shown in Table 1, the mean average of the student's GWA is 1.76, which is interpreted as very good. Looking at the respondents individually, it shows that most of the respondents had an average grade ranging from 1.6 – 2.0 (77.19%), which is interpreted as Very Good, and 1.1 – 1.5 (Superior), with 19.30% of the total respondents. Only 3.51% had a good grade, and no one got excellent or fair. This means that while working, students can balance their studies and maintain good grades. The practice of managing and planning how to divide available time between different activities is known as time management. A person's total performance and accomplishments can be greatly impacted by how well they manage their time. Razali, et al. (2018), indicated that all time management techniques greatly improve students' academic performance. The study makes the case that time management abilities may be crucial for academic achievement, particularly for students in rigorous academic fields like the health sciences. According to one study, students with good time management abilities outperform those with poor time management abilities in terms of their academic performance (Dahm, Glutting, & Young, 2017). Short-term planning involves setting achievable goals and outlining specific actions to reach them within a relatively brief timeframe, typically spanning days to months. It focuses on immediate priorities and resource allocation to ensure efficient progress toward objectives.

Table 2.
Short-term Planning

Indicators	WM	DE
I prioritize tasks based on their urgency and importance.	4.14	Often
I make a daily to-do-list to keep track of my tasks	3.56	Often
I say "no" to non-essential tasks or commitments	3.60	Often
I set specific goals for each day or week	4.18	Often
I prepare the day before I begin	4.09	Often
TOTAL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.19	Often

Equivalent-DE

As shown in Table 2, setting specific goals for each day of work as short-term planning came out to be the highest weighted mean 4.18, or the most preferred technique of the respondents. Based on the study of Ronnie Dotson (2016), he stated that goal setting is the process of giving learning a direction. Additionally, Schunk (2009) makes it clear that while setting goals can increase student motivation and academic achievement, simply outlining a goal does not always have a positive impact on students. However, goal setting has the potential to improve learning if completed effectively. It means that to make a daily to-do list and to keep commitment tasks came out to be only 3.56 which is the lowest of all the statements in the short-term planning. Even though planning appears to underpin many daily activities, researchers have only recently begun to focus on the planning processes involved in everyday problem-solving (Pea & Hawkins et al. 2018). The researchers found out that most of the students do not usually give a to-do list for their daily activities or tasks. They either use their memory instead, or they just take on jobs when they come along. Overwhelming sensations and impaired productivity are frequent effects of this disorganization. The ability of students to manage their time and do well in class can be greatly enhanced by developing the habit of making and using to-do lists.

Table 3.
 Preferred time management techniques of the students in relation to Long-term Planning

Indicators	WM	DE
I maintain my study table free of any items except for what I am presently focusing on.	4.07	Often
I have a targeted schedule for the entire quarter.	3.84	Often
I am working on an assignment until the night before it's due.	3.70	Often
When I have multiple tasks to complete, I tend to allocate each one a small portion of my time.	4.03	Often
I review my notes, even when the exam is not fast approaching.	3.52	Often
TOTAL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.83	Often

Legend: 4 = Equivalent-DE

Table 3 revealed that long-term planning is an effective technique with an overall weighted mean of 3.83 and its description is often. The table shows that working students have fewer long-term plans for their studies and jobs. The statement "Maintain my study table free of any items except for what I am presently focusing on has a weighted mean of 4.07, it has more responses than the other statements. Marella Gimenez (2021) stated that a messy workplace may cause detrimental effects on status and work. However, some working students prefer to study when the examination is not fast approaching, which obtained the lowest actual weighted mean of 3.52. According to David (2022) he states that poor time management is the primary reason why students lack interest in studying. When students do not plan their studies, they tend to accomplish in a limited period. This can lead to procrastination and a lack of interest in studying. It implies that working students have less interest in studying when the examination is not fast approaching.

Table 4.
 Preferred time management techniques of the students in terms of Time Attitude

Indicators	WM	DE
I regularly evaluate and adjust my time management techniques to ensure that it is effective.	4.39	Always
I seek help or delegate tasks when necessary to avoid being overwhelmed.	3.65	Often
I take breaks throughout the day to recharge and avoid burnout.	3.86	Often
I am satisfied with how I manage my time.	3.77	Often
I think there's room for improvement regarding how I handle my time.	4.70	Always
TOTALITY	4.07	Often

Legend: 4.21-5.00= Always, 3.41-4.20= Often, 2.61-3.40= Sometimes, 1.81-2.60= Rarely, 1.00-1.80= Never, Weighted Mean-WM, Descriptive Equivalent-DE

Table 4 revealed that time attitude is an effective technique with an overall weighted mean of 4.07 and interpreted as often. It suggests that working students give value to their time in terms of work and their studies. Abenoja et al. (2019) found out that juggling a social life, family time, school, and employment while studying is surely challenging. Some studies show that part-time students have superior time management skills and are more self-assured than full-time students. The statement "I think there is room for improvement regarding how I handle my time" has the greatest weighted mean of 4.70 and is interpreted as Always. Based on the study of Kosi et al. (2014) as cited by Balacuit et al. (2022), working students can help students develop valuable skills that may improve their chances of finding employment in the future. Additionally, if the task they are given is connected to their area of study, it will motivate them more to strive toward their academic goals. However, some working students seek help or delegate tasks when necessary to avoid being overwhelmed, which obtained the lowest actual weighted mean of 3.65. This means that the working students seek help when necessary so that they will not be overwhelmed by work responsibilities and school obligations.

Table 5.
 Summary of the preferred time management techniques of the working student

Preferred Time Management Techniques	WM	DE
Short-term Planning	3.91	Often
Long-term Planning	3.83	Often
Time Attitudes	4.07	Often

Legend: 4.21-5.00= Always, 3.41-4.20= Often, 2.61-3.40= Sometimes, 1.81-2.60= Rarely, 1.00-1.80= Never, Weighted Mean-WM, Descriptive Equivalent-DE

Based on the result, the preferred technique of the working students was Time Attitude which was the highest 4.07 among the three techniques. Time Attitude refers to students' good or bad attitudes toward the present, future, and past, which has been associated with academic success. On the other hand, attitude governs behavior. Although a person's attitude can be changed, it can also vary depending on the situation, because attitudes can be shaped in a variety of ways, including culture (Douglas, 2002, as quoted in Abun et al., 2019), experience, social variables, conditioning, and observation (Cherry, 2020). This implies that the working students are enhancing efficiency in time management skills.

Table 6.
 Short-term Planning

Coefficient (r):	0.0719907033
N:	57
T statistics:	0.5352862505
DF:	55
p-value:	0.5946097888

The result of solving the Pearson r Correlation was 0.0719907033 or a weak positive correlation. It was implied that the null hypothesis is accepted, and it also means that there is no relation between the preferred time management techniques in relation to short-term planning of the working students to their educational performance. This weak correlation confirms that the working students' school performance is not affected by time management control activities that take place within a daily or weekly time frame. They can schedule and prioritize daily activities and at the same time achieve or gain optimum learning by managing their time skills properly and effectively.

Table 7.
 Long-term Planning

Coefficient (r):	0.1033366532
N:	57
T statistics:	0.7704899972
DF:	55
p-value:	0.4443064543

The result of solving the Pearson r Correlation was 0.1033366532 or a weak positive correlation. It was implied that the null hypothesis is accepted, which also means that there is no relation between long-term planning and school performance in working students. This weak correlation confirms further the working students' academic performance is not affected by how they set long-range goals. They can manage their work and at the same time set long-range goals that require several years which students tend to practice in a year or more.

Table 8.
Time Attitude

Coefficient (r):	0.1648174503
N:	57
T statistics:	1.239267031
DF:	55
p-value:	0.2205089291

The result of solving the Pearson r Correlation was 0.1648174503 or a weak positive correlation. It was implied that the null hypothesis is accepted. It suggests that there is no relation between the preferred time management techniques in relation to the Time Attitude of the working students to their educational Performance. This weak correlation confirms that working students' academic performance is not affected by the way working students feel about their studies and work. They can manage their time at work and at the same time achieve or gain optimum learning by managing their time skills properly and effectively.

In deciding whether the null and alternative hypotheses are to be accepted or rejected, the researchers determine first the level of significance of a one-tailed test by using a 0.05 value of alpha level, which means that researchers only allow for a five percent of error in the data. With this being said, the researchers utilized a 95 percent confidence level. Using the table of the level of significance of a one-tailed test, cross-matching it with the value of the degree of freedom, the p-value is then determined which corresponds to 0.211. Using the critical value 0.211, the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected. This implies that there is a relation between the student's preferred time management techniques to their academic performance. On the contrary, the alternative hypothesis (Ha) is to be accepted. This means that there should be concrete time management used by the students to have a significant increase in their academic performance.

Conclusion:

The study concluded that respondents already implement personal time management techniques, but they are not fully optimized, aligning with Mraovic's 2021 pickle jar theory that uses rocks, pebbles, and sands as variables. It also uncovered a weak positive correlation between time management techniques and academic performance, prompting the proposal of a "Time Management Techniques Enhancement Program." This program aims to improve the effectiveness of time management strategies among working students to enhance their academic achievements.

Recommendation:

The following recommendations were made based on the study's findings and results and the researchers highly suggest the following: 1. It is recommended that the proposed program be utilized and used by the target respondents to evaluate its effectiveness. 2. The study suggested that future researchers may involve the School of Business and the School of Technology to examine the time management techniques of the students from other departments. 3. Further, studies involve qualitative methods employing phenomenology to explore the lived experiences of working students concerning time management and qualitative methods employing case study design to assess the Preferred Time Management Techniques among working students. 4. Future researchers related to Preferred Time Management Techniques would involve the total population to gather additional insight into its significance, especially working students.

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APPENDIX D

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Name of Grammarian: Melojie R. Lauron

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This is to certify that the study entitled "Preferred Time Management Techniques Among Working Students" of Laiza Candelasa, Angelica Talledo, Jenelyn Villarante, Rhea Mae Apawan, Haydee Evardone - Bachelor of Elementary Education students of Mandaue City College has been checked by Melojie R. Lauron as Grammarian.

This certification is issued upon request of the group as part of their oral defense requirements.
Given this 19nd day of June 2023.

MELIJE R. LAURON

Signature over the printed name
Grammarian

APPENDIX E

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CLEARANCE FROM RESEARCH CENSOR

The research entitled “Proffered Time Management Techniques Among Working Students ” prepared and submitted by, Laiza P. Candelasa, Angelica C Talledo, Jenelyn G. Villrante, Rhea Mae L. Apawan, Haydee D. Evardone , has been thoroughly read and corrected by me as the Research Censor and the manuscript has been edited by the student-researchers.

After compliance with the comments and suggestions given, they have made revisions which are now considered to meet the standard for a quality research output.

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